

PERCEPTION OF HEARING IMPAIRED STUDENTS ON PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT FROM THE ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECT OF FAMILY, PEERS AND SCHOOL ENVIRONMENTS

*Nancy Anthony (nancyant@siswa.ukm.edu.my)
Faculty of Education, The National University of Malaysia,
Bangi, Selangor, 43600, Malaysia*

*Dr Safani Bari (safani@ukm.edu.my)
Faculty of Education, The National University of Malaysia,
Bangi, Selangor, 43600, Malaysia*

Abstract

Parental involvement in a child's life affects the development of a child. It includes attitude in disciplining children, love, acceptance and concerns from parents to children. This study aims to evaluate the perception of hearing impaired students on parental involvement in terms of family environment, peers and school environments. The study was conducted at two integrated special education programs (deaf) in secondary school in Sabah, Malaysia. A total of 95 students has been involved in the study. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS). Descriptive analyzes included frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations were used. The results showed that 80.4% of respondents said that parents / guardians are always showing their affection to the children, 57.7% of parents / guardians give freedom to the children to go out to meet with friends and 58.8% of parents / guardians recognize their friend's parents in school. However, guidance and support from various parties need to be improved to assist parents in educating and supporting their children who are hearing impaired.

Keywords: Parents involvement- hearing impaired students

Introduction

Parental involvement in children's lives has an important influence in a child's development. Therefore the establishment of a parent toolkit in in Education Development Blueprint (EDPM) 2013 – 2025 was a major initiative of the Malaysian Education. Subsequently, under the parent's toolkit initiative, the parents would be provided with the tools so that they could become active partners in their children's learning so that their performance and achievement could be improved. It not only helps to increase parental involvement in children's learning in and outside school, but also promotes excellence in the future.

Parent involvement

According to Epstein (2009), parental involvement includes the role of parents towards their children at home, school and community activities (namely, the duty of parents, communities, voluntary activities at school, involvement in children's learning at home and collaborate with the community). Each type of involvement includes a variety of practices to be carried out by teachers, parents, and students in theory and is association with a variety of different outcomes for students, teachers, and parents as well. Moreover, it also refers to the relationship and parental support for their children's lives, such as speech therapy, physical therapy and children self-management skills (Heath, 2013).

Hearing Impaired Students

The term hearing problems' is commonly used by the medical (clinical) and education sectors. children who are as deaf may still have residual hearing (Clark, 1999). According to Cruickshank and Johnson (1975), hearing problems are divided into two categories, deaf and partially deaf (two categories of deafness is severe and profound). Partial deafness occurs when there is damage to hearing, but hearing aids can help in restoring hearing loss.

The level of hearing loss measurements used in Malaysia is based on the category of hearing loss that is used by the Department of Audiology and Speech Sciences, Hospital Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (HUKM) as detailed in Table 1 below:

Table 1 - Classification of hearing loss

The degree of loss (Decibels /dB)	Categories of hearing loss	Description
Below 20 dB	Normal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The degree of hearing loss is normal and can hear all the noise. • Categorized as normal.
21 – 45 dB	Mild	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It's hard to hear the soft sounds from a long distance. • Categorized as normal.
46 – 70 dB	Moderate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ability to hear sounds between 1 to 1.5 meters. • Must speak out loud when communicating with them. • Their speech is less clear. • Categorized as normal.
71 – 90 dB	Severe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unable to hear normal speech. • Having severe speech problems. • Categorized as hearing impaired.
Above 91 dB	Profound	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not heard even louder sound. • Having severe speech problems. • Categorized as hearing impaired.

Hearing classification shows some level of hearing loss. A person with a hearing loss of 20 dB and below is considered normal because he can still hear all the noise. For individuals with a hearing loss of 21-45 dB, he will be in the mild category as difficult to hear the soft sound from a long distance. But he is still considered an ordinary person (person with normal hearing). If the person loses 46-70 dB of hearing, he could still hear the sound of the distance between 1 to 1.5 meters. However, we need to speak out loud when communicating with them. In addition, they also speak less clearly. However, all of them are also classified as normal and do not need to learn in special schools.

A person with severe hearing loss of 71-90 dB classified as hearing impaired have severe speech problems because they cannot even hear a loud sound and will miss the vast majority of conversational. For a person with profound hearing loss of 91dB and more cannot hear speech sounds even if they are very loud. Severe and profound hearing loss students will learn in special schools or integration school programs.

Purpose of the study are:

To identify the perception of hearing impaired students about the involvement of parents in the family aspect.

To identify the perception of hearing impaired students about the involvement of parents in their peer aspect.

To identify the perception of hearing impaired students about the involvement of parents in school environment aspect.

Problems statement

The responsibility of parents in educating children with special needs poses a major challenge, especially in the facing an emotional development of the child. The various reactions and perceptions of among parents regarding the problems experienced by their children. Most mothers expressed similar concerns about the level of hearing problems experienced by children that may affect the future of the family and worry that their children do not given equal opportunities in life (Quittner, Barker, Cruz, Snell, Grimley & Botteri, 2010).

In addition, they also lack knowledge of child disabilities, communication methods used in the family as well as a source of information that can support the family and their child (Fitzpatrick, Angus, Durieux-Smith, Graham & Coyle, 2008). Parents who have children with hearing problems are really faced with many challenges in understanding their child's emotional development. Review by Plotkin, Brice and Reesman (2013) dealing with the parents' stress who have children with hearing problems they faced problems in taking responsibility for their children and felt marginalized from society.

Parental behavior also affects their involvement in their children's lives. Review by Antonopoulou, Hadjidakou, Stampoltzis and Nicolaou (2012) found that there are certain features of parental behavior that shows their child's emotional misunderstanding. Rejection by parents happen when they intentionally did not recognize that their child needs help or not to accept the situation of children deemed imperfect.

Method

Researchers conducting quantitative research survey using a questionnaire as an instrument chose to investigate the perception of hearing impaired students about their parent involvement in the family, peers and school environments aspects. The questionnaire consists of four parts, namely Part A contains background information on the respondents. Part B also assesses the perception of hearing impaired students of parent involvement in family aspect. While Part C, hearing impaired students' perception of parental involvement in aspects of their peers and Part D, hearing impaired students' perception of parent involvement in school environment aspect. The response was assessed according to five Likert scale classification very satisfied, satisfied, moderate, unsatisfied and very unsatisfied. The sample consisted of 97 hearing impaired students in a special education integration program in two secondary schools in Sabah, Malaysia.

The data in this study were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 21. Score for Part A respondent summed to obtain percentages by category of gender, home location, and number of siblings. The data in sections B, C and D is accumulated and aggregated in a frequency and percentage to determine the number and percentage of respondents who very unsatisfied, unsatisfied, moderate, satisfied and very satisfied with items that have been specified in the questionnaire. For the analysis of Likert scale, depending maximum range has been divided into three, namely a mean score of 1.00 to 2.33 as low, 2.34 to 3.66 mean as medium and 3.67 to 5.00 as the highest level (Jamil, 2002).

Findings

Analysis of the findings of the hearing impaired students' perceptions of parental involvement based on the following items.

Demographics of Respondents

The study involved a total of 97 secondary school pupils who have hearing problems with various backgrounds such as gender, home location and number of siblings. Demographic profile is shown in Table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1 - Demographic profile of respondents

Demography	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Gender</i>		
Males	60	61.9%
Females	37	38.1%
<i>Home location</i>		
Town	47	48.5%
Rural	50	51.5%
<i>Number of siblings</i>		
1 to 2 people	6	6.2%
3 to 4 people	20	20.6%
5 to 6 people	33	34.0%
6 people and more	38	39.2%
<i>n = 97</i>		

Table 4.1 shows that based on gender, a total of 60 respondents (61.9%) males and a total of 37 respondents (38.1%) was female students. Based on the location of the house, a total of 47 (48.5%) students with a home location in the city and a total of 50 (51.5%) of students living in rural areas. Information on the number of siblings showed a total of 6 (6.2%) students with the number of siblings of 1 to 2 people, 20 (20.6%) students with the number of siblings 3 to 4 people, a total of 33 (34.0%) students with the number of siblings 5 to 6 people and a total of 38 (39.2%) students with the number of siblings more than 6 people.

Hearing problems students' perception of Parent Involvement in family aspect

Table 4.2 - Level of involvement of the parents in family aspect

No	Aspects of Family Item	Very Unsatisfi ed	Unsatisfi ed	Medium Satisfie d	Very satisfie d	Mean	SD	Interp.
1.	Parents / guardians are always take care about yourself.	3 (3.1%)	9 (9.3%)	43 (44.3%)	31 (32.0%)	11 (11.3%)	3.39	0.92 Moderate
2.	Parents / guardians always gave support to the activities in which you participate.	10 (10.3%)	12 (12.4%)	26 (26.8%)	17 (17.5%)	32 (33.0%)	3.51	1.34 Moderate
3.	Parents / guardians always involve you and your siblings with activities at home.	7 (7.2%)	10 (10.3%)	18 (18.6%)	29 (29.9%)	33 (34.0%)	3.73	1.24 High
4.	Parents / guardians are always encouraged you and other siblings work together to complete the work at home.	8 (8.2%)	10 (10.3%)	24 (24.7%)	38 (39.2%)	17 (17.5%)	3.47	1.15 Moderate
	Parents / guardians are always showing their affection to you.	1 (1.0%)	9 (9.3%)	9 (9.3%)	22 (22.7%)	56 (57.7%)	4.27	1.04 High
Total							3.67	0.70 High

n=97

Table 4.2 shows the items that have the highest mean is that parents / guardians are always showing their affection to you (mean = 4.27 and SD = 1.04) remained at a high level. In terms of frequencies and percentages show that 56 (57.7%) students expressed very satisfactory, a total of 22 (22.7%) students expressed satisfaction, 9 of them (9.3%) expressed a moderate, 9 of the (9.3%) students expressed not satisfactory and as many as one person (1.0%) students expressed very unsatisfactory. Items that have the lowest mean is that parents / guardians always take out about yourself (mean = 3.39 and SP = 0.92) at a moderate level. In terms of frequency and percentage shows a total of 43 (44.3%) students stated moderate, a total of 31 (32.0%) students expressed satisfaction, a total of 11 patients (11.3%) students expressed very satisfying, 9 of the (9.3%) students expressed not satisfying and only 3 (3.1%) students expressed very unsatisfactory. Overall shown that the involvement of the parents of the family was at a high level (mean = 3.67 and SP = 0.70).

Hearing problems students' perception of Parent Involvement in peer aspect

Table 4.3 - Level of involvement of the parents in peer aspect

No	Aspects of Peers Item	Very Unsatisfied	Unsatisfied	Medium	Satisfied	Very satisfied	Mean	SD	Interp.
1.	Parents / guardians recognize your friends.	5 (5.2%)	9 (9.3%)	35 (36.1%)	31 (32.0%)	17 (17.5%)	3.47	1.05	Moderate
2.	Parents / guardians give you the freedom to go out to meet with friends.	5 (5.2%)	14 (14.4%)	22 (22.7%)	32 (33.0%)	24 (24.7%)	3.58	1.16	Moderate
3.	Parents / guardians are always taking time to do activities together with you and your friends.	8 (8.2%)	16 (16.5%)	31 (32.0%)	28 (28.9%)	14 (14.4%)	3.25	1.15	Moderate
4.	Parents / guardians discussing / sharing / tell stories with you.	9 (9.3%)	13 (13.4%)	23 (23.7%)	28 (28.9%)	24 (24.7%)	3.46	1.26	Moderate
5.	Parents / guardians always control your moves if you want to leave to meet with friends.	10 (10.3%)	10 (10.3%)	26 (26.8%)	32 (33.0%)	19 (19.6%)	3.41	1.21	Moderate
Total							3.44	0.70	Moderate

n = 97

Table 4.3 shows that the item that has the highest mean is that parents / guardians give you the freedom to go out to meet with your friends (mean = 3.58 and SD = 1.16) at a moderate level. In terms of frequency and percentage shows a total of 32 (33.0%) students expressed satisfaction, 24 (24.7%) students expressed very satisfactory, a total of 22 (22.7%) students stated moderate, a total of 14 (14.4%) students expressed not satisfactory and a total of 5 (5.2%) students expressed very unsatisfactory. Items that have the lowest mean is that parents / guardians always take the time to do activities together with you and your friends (mean = 3.25 and SD = 1.15) at a moderate level. In terms of frequency and percentage shows a total of 31 (32.0%) students stated moderate, a total of 28 (28.9%) students expressed satisfaction, a total of 16 (16.5%) students stated unsatisfactory, a total of 14 (14.4%) students stated very satisfactory and a total of 8 (8.2%) students expressed very unsatisfactory. Overall shown that the involvement of parents in terms of their peers at a moderate level (mean = 3.44 and SD = 0.70).

Hearing problems students' perception of parent involvement in school environments aspect

Table 4.4 - Level of involvement of the parents in school environments aspect

No	Aspects of School Environments Item	Very Unsatisfied	Unsatisfied	Medium	Satisfied	Very satisfied	Mean	SD	Interp.
1.	Parents / guardians are always present in your activities at school.	10 (10.3%)	13 (13.4%)	24 (24.7%)	27 (27.8%)	23 (23.7%)	3.41	1.27	Moderate
2.	Parents / guardians are always giving ideas / support to you.	10 (10.3%)	14 (14.4%)	29 (29.9%)	26 (26.8%)	18 (18.6%)	3.29	1.22	Moderate
3.	Parents / guardians are always guiding you to complete the task of the school.	6 (6.2%)	11 (11.3%)	34 (35.1%)	32 (33.0%)	14 (14.4%)	3.38	1.07	Moderate
4.	Parent / guardian provides additional guidance / tuition for you.	12 (12.4%)	15 (15.5%)	37 (38.1%)	19 (19.6%)	14 (14.4%)	3.08	1.20	Moderate
5.	Parents / guardians recognize the parents of your friends at school.	5 (5.2%)	8 (8.2%)	28 (28.9%)	29 (29.9%)	27 (27.8%)	3.67	1.13	High
Total							3.37	0.67	Moderate

n=97

Table 4.4 shows that every item that has the highest mean is that parents / guardians recognize the parents of your friends in school (mean = 3.67 and SD = 1.13) remained at a high level. In terms of frequencies and percentages indicate a total of 29 (29.9%) students expressed satisfaction, a total of 28 (28.9%) students stated moderate, as much as 27 (27.8%) students stated very satisfactory, a total of 8 (8.2%) students said it was not satisfied and a total of 5 (5.2%) students stated very unsatisfactory. Items that have the lowest mean is Parent / guardian provides additional guidance / tuition for you (mean = 3.08 and SD = 1.20) at a moderate level. In terms of frequencies and percentages indicate a total of 37 (38.1%) students stated moderate, as many as 19 (19.6%) students expressed satisfaction, a total of 15 (15.5%) students stated not satisfactory, a total of 14 (14.4%) students stated very satisfactory and as many as 12 (12.4%) students stated very unsatisfactory. Overall shown that the involvement of parents from the school environment aspects were at a moderate level (mean = 3.37 and SD = 0.67).

Discussion

The highest mean of parental involvement in the emotional development of students with hearing problems from the aspects of the family is that parents / guardians are always showing their affection to the students. This finding is consistent with studies that have been conducted by Antonopoulou et.al (2012) in Cyprus, stating that parents who have children with hearing problems and devote particular care to their children because they want to help social development and emotionally balanced for their children so that the children feel accepted and loved by their parents.

The parental involvement in the peer aspect shows that the item that have the highest mean is that parents / guardians give freedom to their children to go out to meet their friends. According to a study conducted by Batten, Oakes and Alexander (2013), the attitude of the parents is to provide opportunities for children to socialize and interact with their peers and others. Beside that, it also fosters friendships between partners in order to help each other and share experience. It not only can improve children's motivation, but also a positive self-esteem can be formed.

The study also found that parental involvement in terms of school environment that has the highest mean is parents / guardians parents recognize their child's friends at school. According to a study conducted by Heath (2013) about the relationship between parents and children showed that parental attitudes is important because it can provide an opportunity for parents to exchange experiences and opinions in addressing hearing impaired children. Furthermore, most of the hearing impaired children are having parents who can hear and they need support from other parents in educating their children and caring for the hearing impaired (Broussard & Mathos, 2005)

Conclusions

The results of the perception among students showed that 80.4 % of parents / guardians who always show their affection to their children, 57.7 % parents / guardians who give freedom to their children and only 57.7 % of the parents / guardians who recognize the other parents. Thus the implications of this study indicate the need for counselling and support for parents to be involved in supporting their child's development in various aspects that can help not only the children excellence in academics but also in the face of various challenges in life.

References

- Antonopoulou, K., Hadjikakou, K., Stampoltzis, A. & Nicolaou, N. 2012. Parenting styles of mothers with deaf or hard-of-hearing children and hearing siblings. *Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 17(3), 306-308.
- Batten, G., Oakes, P. M., & Alexander, Tim. 2013. Factors associated with social interactions between deaf children and their hearing peers: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 19(3), 285-302.
- Broussard, E.R., & Mathos, K.K. 2005. Outlining the concerns of children who have hearing loss and their families. *Journal of American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 44(1), 96-100.
- Clark, M. 1999. Language through daily living for hearing impaired children. London: British Library Cataloging in Publication Data.
- Cruikshank, W. M., & Johnson, G. O. 1975. Education of exceptional children and youth. Edisi ke 3. New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- Epstein, J. L. 2009. *In school, family and community partnership: Your handbook for action*. Edisi ke 3. United States of America: Corwin Press.
- Fitzpatrick, E., Angus, D., Durieux-Smith, A., Graham, I., & Coyle, D. 2008. Parent's need following identification of childhood hearing loss.. *American Journal of Audiology*, 17, 38-49.
- Heath, P. 2013. *Parent-child relations*. Edisi ke 3. Pearson.
- Jamil Ahmad. 2002. *Pemupukan budaya penyelidikan di kalangan guru di sekolah: Satu penilaian*. Tesis Doktor Falsafah Fakulti Pendidikan Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.
- Quittner, A. I., Barker, D. H., Cruz, I., Snell, C., Grimley, M. E. & Botteri. 2010. Parenting stress among parents of deaf and hearing children: Association with language delays and behavior problems. *Parenting*, 10, 136-155.